

A METHOD OF PREPARING MONO-ETHERS OF METHYLENEGLYCOL.

BY M. L. GUPTA, R. KAUSHAL, AND S. S. DESHPANDE.

By the action of chloromethyl acetate on sodium derivative of an alcohol, an ether acetate of methyleneglycol results, from which on alkali hydrolysis the corresponding mono-ether is obtained. The preparation of the monobenzyl ether is described.

Methyleneglycol (I) is not known. Its mono-ethers (II) are not described in literature. Its diethers (III) are the acetals of formaldehyde, and, when symmetrical ($R=R'$), are obtained by the usual process of con-

densing the aldehyde with alcohols. Among its unsymmetrical diethers the better known are the methyl ethers which are obtained by condensing monochloromethyl ether with sodium derivative of an alcohol.

The mono-ethers (II) cannot be prepared by the action of dilute aqueous alkali on a halogen ether such as the iodoether $\text{R-O-CH}_2\text{I}$ (V) (which might result from (IV) by fission with HI]. For, as has been shown by Wedekind (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 814; 1903, **36**, 1354) the halogen ethers (V) are decomposed by water giving formaldehyde. Thus chloromethyl menthyl ether gives menthol, formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid (*ibid.*, 1903, **34**, 814).

If, however, the sodium derivative of an alcohol is condensed with chloromethyl acetate the resulting compound will be an ether acetate of methyleneglycol.

The ester part of (VI) could be hydrolysed by alkali which will not attack the ether link, and the desired mono-ether of methyleneglycol will result.

This plan worked, and the monobenzyl ether of methyleneglycol (II, $R = C_6H_5-CH_2-$) was prepared in a fairly good yield through the acetate (VI) ($R = C_6H_5-CH_2-$) which in its turn was obtained from sodium derivative of benzyl alcohol and chloromethyl acetate.

Benzyl ether of methyleneglycol is a liquid, somewhat soluble in water. It is characterised by the formation of its phenylurethane, which is readily obtained. Nitric acid oxidises the ether to benzoic acid.

During the course of the work the unsymmetrical methylbenzyl ether of methyleneglycol has been prepared by the method shown for formation of (IV). This compound has not so far been described. In a Zeisel estimation it gives theoretical yield of methyl iodide.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Chloromethyl acetate was prepared by the method of Desende (*Compt. rend.*, 1901, 132, 1568). Acetyl chloride (13 g.) and trioxymethylene (15 g.) were refluxed in presence of zinc chloride and the product of reaction was distilled at reduced pressure when 11 g. of a liquid boiling at $58^{\circ}-62^{\circ}/29\text{cm.}$ was obtained.

The Acetate of Methyleneglycol monobenzyl Ether (VI, $R = C_6H_5-CH_2-$).—Benzyl alcohol (8.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene and equivalent amount of sodium (in the form of wire) was added. On refluxing for 3 hours on a water-bath, a white suspension of the sodium derivative of benzyl alcohol was obtained. Chloromethyl acetate (11 g.) was then gradually added and the whole refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours. The sodium chloride formed was filtered off and benzene distilled from the filtrate. The remaining liquid was then distilled under reduced pressure when a fraction boiling between $152^{\circ}-55^{\circ}/29\text{ mm.}$ was obtained, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 6.2. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.7 per cent).

The acetate is a thin liquid with a somewhat penetrating odour resembling that of formalin.

Methyleneglycol monobenzyl Ether (II, $R = C_6H_5-CH_2-$).—The acetate (2 g.) was hydrolysed with potassium hydroxide (1 g. dissolved in 10 c.c. of 90% alcohol) by refluxing on a water-bath for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with ether. On drying and removing the solvent the remaining liquid was distilled under reduced pressure, when the monobenzyl ether passed between $75^{\circ}-77^{\circ}/4\text{ mm.}$ (Found: C, 69.3; H, 7.3. $C_8H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 69.6; H, 7.3 per cent).

The monobenzyl ether is a thin liquid, somewhat soluble in water and has a faint sweet odour. With phenylisocyanate it readily gave the phenyl-

urethane, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 75°. (Found: N, 5'45. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 5'15 per cent).

With concentrated nitric acid and a drop of sulphuric acid the mono-benzyl ether was oxidised to benzoic acid which was identified by its melting point and its equivalent weight.

Methyleneglycol methylbenzyl Ether (IV, $R = C_6H_5-CH_2-$).—Sodium derivative of benzyl alcohol, obtained from 10'8 g. of the alcohol and equivalent amount of sodium, was suspended in dry benzene and monochloromethyl ether (12 g.) was added, and the whole was refluxed until the reaction mixture was neutral (3 hours). On filtering and distilling off the solvent the remaining liquid was distilled under reduced pressure when two fractions were obtained :

(i) B.p. 84°-87°/8 mm. (3 g.)

(ii) B.p. 165°-67°/8 mm. (3 g.)

Fraction (ii) was not investigated. Fraction (i) was analysed. (Found: C, 70'3; H, 7'3; OMe, 19'6. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71'0; H, 7'9; OMe, 20'4 per cent).

CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
HOLKAR COLLEGE,
INDORE.

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